

ROBOT OPERATED PAINTING MACHINE USING SYSTEM SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of spray painting robot controlled machine through computer simulation. The operations of robot and spray was controlled by system and operated by pneumatic controller. To operate the robot, program was written using VB. The spray was utilized to paint the surfaces which were not feasible to operate by humans. Signals are processed using a relay in external electronic circuit. This will control any operations of the device. The robot can move forward, backward, left and right. This device can be used to paint any vehicle in any place in future this can be implemented with artificial intelligence which can paint automatically

KEY POINTS: computer simulations, robot, VB, ECU.